

Hardening Amazon Web Service OTA Update Process

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Abstract. As number of the IoT (Internet of Things) devices continues to increase it becomes crucial to provide scalable and secure update mechanism. In this paper we present our improvements of the Amazon over-the-air (OTA) update process specifically targeting existing IoT devices. We want to cover broad range of device retrofitting them and making them more secure. Keeping this in mind we keep hardware requirements to minimum. We present our improvements over default Amazon OTA Agent library implementation as well as our reference implementation on STMicroelectronics B-L475E-IOT01A board. We also discuss limits of our selected approach and potential attacks not covered by it.

Keywords: OTA update, IoT, Amazon, STM32L475VG, mbedTLS

1 Introduction

In the recent years, IoT devices are becoming more and more common in our everyday lives. According to the forecasts, number of connected IoT devices could achieve 20.4 billion by the end of 2020 [8]. As the IoT devices gain popularity and widespread usage it becomes increasingly important that they implement proper security measures and that security of devices is maintained through their lifetime by periodic updates. Insecure IoT devices can open wide variety of attacks such as coordinated DOS attacks, information leaks and they could be even subjects to intentional bricking. These attacks can be especially devastating due to sheer number of devices being left vulnerable once security issues are discovered. For example, Mirai botnet in 2016 hijacked over 900.000 routers from Deutsche Telekom [10]. IoT devices are also often left running unattended for long periods of time which additionally increases security risk.

The techniques like static analysis and fuzzing can help mitigate and fix large number of potential security issues, if properly applied, even before device hits market. However, even with the help of these techniques, it is unfeasible to consider that deployed devices will be free of software defects. IoT devices are often mass deployed or deployed in inaccessible locations making it impractical to retrieve all of the devices and patch them once the security issues are detected. For given reasons, increasing importance is given to over-the-air (OTA) update process as a cheap and, if properly implemented, secure way to handle

IoT device updates. In this paper we have focused on the Amazon OTA update process mechanism due to large market adoption of Amazon FreeRTOS. Amazon FreeRTOS is embedded software stack based on open source FreeRTOS with integrated AWS (Amazon Web Services) libraries. In a survey performed in 2017 FreeRTOS had the second largest market share with 20%, only 2% less than Embedded Linux, and the highest predicted growth [1]. OTA update implementations are often dependant on hardware security features provided by IoT devices themselves, but Amazon FreeRTOS OTA update as well as our additional improvements assume minimal set of required features making this approach suitable for retrofitting existing devices. This is especially important as most of mass deployed IoT devices are cheap and often lacking in terms of inbuilt security features.

Contributions: The main contribution of our work is two-fold, the analysis of current state of OTA Agent library security measures as well as suggestion and implementation of the suggested hardening approach. We encrypt application images using ChaCha20 encryption before storing them on the Amazon S3, providing additional security from the server side. On client, IoT side, we use SRAM PUF as a flexible and retroactively applicable mean of protection for required symmetric ChaCha20 key.

Paper Outline: In Chapter 2 we first describe the workflow of current Amazon OTA update process. We focus on inner workings of Amazon OTA Agent library and on procedure for scheduling Amazon OTA jobs using AWS CLI. Our improvements to presented Amazon OTA update workflow are described in Chapter 3. In chapter 4, we go into details of our reference implementation based on STMicroelectronics B-L475E-IOT01A board. Conclusion of this paper is provided in Chapter 5.

2 Amazon OTA Agent Library Analysis

To better understand our improvements to the Amazon OTA update process, first we have to understand inner workings of the default Amazon implementation and how all required components are connected together. In order to help developers to implement and integrate OTA updates faster in their projects, Amazon has released the OTA Agent, a library implementing key functionality required for updates [2]. Currently Amazon provides support for only few selected boards, but due to its design choices OTA Agent is easily portable. All platform specific functions used by the OTA Agent are separated from main code in platform abstraction layer (PAL) located in `aws_ota_pal.c`¹. General architecture of the Amazon FreeRTOS is shown on Figure 1.

Although OTA Agent presents main component of update process, it also depends on bootloader and on update servers which combined constitute the whole OTA update mechanism. Similar as with OTA Agent library itself, Amazon has releases reference bootloaders for selected boards while providing guidelines for

¹ `<amazon-freertos>/vendors/<vendor>/boards/<board>/ports/ota/aws_ota_pal.c`

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Amazon FreeRTOS [14]

implementation on different platforms. Once all components are ported the OTA agent can simply be used by initializing the OTA Agent instance and implementing callback functions scheduling a device restart in suitable time, in case of a successful download of the new application image. In the rest of this section we will describe in more detail inner workings of the OTA Agent library and the procedure for creating server AWS IoT job for serving updates.

2.1 Amazon OTA Agent Library Flow

Upon being initialized (`OTA_AgentInit`), OTA Agent will create a new FreeRTOS task which will reuse provided Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) connection to subscribe to the required topics. MQTT is a lightweight messaging protocol based on publish-subscribe pattern designed for constrained devices. As MQTT is already used to communicate with Amazon servers, connection reuse reduces OTA Agent RAM footprint significantly. OTA Agent initially connects to two topics: `$aws/things/<thing_name>/jobs/$next/get/accepted` and `$aws/things/<thing_name>/jobs/notify-next`. The first topic serves notifications about updates in progress and the second serves notifications regarding new updates.

Once subscribed, OTA Agent will check for new update by sending `{"clientToken": "<request_id>:<thing_name>"}` message to the `notify-next` MQTT topic after which it will wait in background for notification from server. Initialization of the board and OTA Agent library is shown in Appendix A (Figure 4). When server has a new update to serve it will send a JSON formatted message containing all the update meta-data to OTA Agent which will parse

it and fill file context struct (`OTA_FileContext_t`). Using a combination of stream name from received JSON message and device name the OTA Agent will connect to the additional MQTT topic, which will provide the data stream for upcoming update. Simplified version of the `OTA_FileContext_t` struct is shown in Listing 1.1.

```

1 typedef struct
2 {
3     uint8_t * pucFilePath;
4     union
5     {
6         int32_t lFileHandle;
7         uint8_t * pucFile;
8     };
9     uint32_t ulFileSize;
10    uint32_t ulBlocksRemaining;
11    uint8_t * pucJobName;
12    uint8_t * pucStreamName;
13    Sig256_t * pxSignature;
14    uint8_t * pucRxBlockBitmap;
15    uint8_t * pucCertFilepath;
16    uint32_t ulUpdaterVersion;
17    bool_t xIsInSelfTest;
18 } OTA_FileContext_t;

```

Listing 1.1. `OTA_FileContext_t` structure

Described structure is passed to the PAL layer function which is responsible for creating a new file to store the update or, in case that the files are not supported, returning the flash address that should be used to store the update (`prvPAL_CreateFileForRx`). If the update is accepted, the OTA Agent will start receiving packets from server in chunks of predefined size and passing them to `prvPAL_WriteBlock` function to be stored on device. Chunk size and other OTA Agent configuration parameters are set in `aws_ota_agent_config.h`². Once all the chunks are received, `prvPAL_CloseFile` function is called to validate if the file is correct by checking its signature. After validation the OTA Agent will activate the callback function provided during initialization notifying the application about the result of update and outsourcing task of scheduling software restart to it. Restart is performed using `OTA_ActivateNewImage` function which internally calls `prvPAL_ActivateNewImage` implementing board specific restart functionality.

During the startup, the bootloader decides which image should be booted and validate it. Memory layout of reference implementation on the B-L475E-IOT01A board is shown on Figure 2. Validation consists of multiple checks, image metadata, header and lastly application signature are all re-validated. Bootloader also activates watchdog timer causing board to shutdown and mark application as

² `<amazon-freertos>/vendors/<vendor>/boards/<board>/aws_demos/config_files/aws_ota_agent_config.h`

Fig. 2. Memory layout used in our reference implementation

invalid if application doesn't self validate in time. After FreeRTOS is restarted, OTA Agent library activates user provided callback informing the application that the image is in self-test phase and that it should self validate. Self validation is board specific and should be implemented by user. If successful, user callback should call **OTA_SetImageState** with **eOTA_ImageState_Accepted** as an argument. This will cause OTA Agent to stop activated watchdog timer and mark update job as completed, finishing the process. Default Amazon OTA update flow is depicted on Figure 3.

Full list of necessary PAL functions that have to be implemented in order to port the OTA Agent library is given in the Table 1.

Function	Description
prvPAL_Abort	Aborts an OTA update.
prvPAL_CreateFileForRx	Creates a file to store incoming data chunks.
prvPAL_CloseFile	Closes the specified file and verify signature if enabled.
prvPAL_WriteBlock	Writes a data chunk to the specified file at the given offset.
prvPAL_ActivateNewImage	Activates or launches the new firmware image.
prvPAL_SetPlatformImageState	Handles platform specific actions related to if new image should be accepted or rejected.
prvPAL_GetPlatformImageState	Gets the state of the OTA update.
prvPAL_ResetDevice	Resets the device.

Table 1. PAL layer functions

Fig. 3. Amazon OTA update flow diagram

2.2 AWS OTA Job

The OTA Update Manager Service [11] is responsible for managing all aspects of the Amazon OTA update process. It provides APIs enabling creation, deletion, listing and retrieving information of OTA updates. We can access Amazon OTA Update Manager Service using Amazon Console or in more automated way using provided AWS CLI (console line interface) [5]. As example we will demonstrate how to create a OTA update job using CLI. Creation of a OTA update job using boto3, an Amazon Web Services (AWS) SDK for Python [6], is similar to the described procedure.

The following procedure assumes that AWS CLI is properly configured using **aws configure** CLI command and that required roles and role permissions are set. The first step in update creation is uploading new application image file to S3 bucket:

```
1 aws s3 cp <local_file> s3://<bucket_name>/<file_name>
```

Once the image is uploaded we can create stream using appropriate role:

```
1 aws iot create-stream --stream-id <random_id> --description <
  description> --files file://stream.json --role <role_ARN>
```

The structure of stream.json is shown below:

```

1 [{
2   "fileId": 0,
3   "s3Location": {
4     "bucket": <bucket_name>,
5     "key": <file_name>
6   }
7 }]

```

After the stream is created we can proceed with creation of the OTA update. In this example we will use an image which is signed locally and provide to Amazon a corresponding image signature. Once OTA update is created the OTA Update Manager Service will create AWS IoT job responsible for notifying devices about update availability.

```

1 aws iot create-ota-update --ota-update-id <random_id> --
   target-selection SNAPSHOT --description <description> --
   targets <thing_or_thing_group_ARN> --role <role_ARN> --
   file file://ota.json

```

The structure of ota.json is shown below:

```

1 [{
2   "fileName": <file_name>,
3   "fileLocation": {
4     "stream": {
5       "streamId": <stream_id>,
6       "fileId": 0
7     }
8   },
9   "codeSigning": {
10    "customCodeSigning": {
11      "signature": {
12        "inlineDocument": <base64_signature>
13      },
14      "certificateChain": {
15        "certificateName": <certificate_name>
16      },
17      "hashAlgorithm": "sha256",
18      "signatureAlgorithm": "ecdsa"
19    }
20  }
21 }]

```

More detailed explanations and alternative options are described in Amazon's documentation [4].

3 AWS OTA Update Process Improvements

One of the key issues with the current Amazon OTA process, which we are addressing, is that the Amazon is assumed as the trusted party. Amazon's servers

will encrypt the images during transfer by relaying on MQTT over TLS when sending data to device, however on Amazon S3 the data will be unprotected. Also, Amazon provides ability to use Amazon-generated keys for signing, which increases the ease of deployment but additionally decreases the security. Attacker, with access to Amazon, could encrypt their own images and deploy them if this signing option is used. Even if we use our own keys to sign an image, results in having unencrypted image in Amazon's cloud which in turn opens possibility of the reverse engineering with the goal of vulnerability finding or performing theft of intellectual property (IP). Although it could be argued that, as we relay on Amazon, this does not incur additional security risk, it still leaves potential security vulnerability. Amazon S3 has already been breached in the past [13] and there is always possibility of state actors compelling Amazon to hand over the data. Moreover, described issues are not Amazon specific and are applicable to all cases in which distribution of images is done via third party. Having completely encrypted image is especially useful in combination of end-to-end encryption between devices and MQTT clients in which way we are essentially using Amazon only as transport layer without leaking any unencrypted data.

Amazon servers work with whole firmware images and perform splitting of image in chunks only when serving data to the devices during the update. This approach makes using block cipher approach impractical if we want to decrypt blocks as soon as they are received. Alternative approach is to store encrypted image in flash and decrypt it before running. In this way we would achieve additional security but it would also mean that our target device has to have enough SRAM to store whole unencrypted image while keeping enough SRAM for stack and heap during runtime. As we have targeted resource-constrained devices this approach was unfeasible. STM32L475VG board which was used for our reference implementation possesses 128KB of SRAM while size of the FreeRTOS image we are running on it is around 400KB. As a workaround we decided to use stream ciphers, specifically ChaCha20. ChaCha20 is a modification of the Salsa20 stream cipher, which was also developed by Daniel J. Bernstein and was published in 2008. It is widely adopted and was added in TLS cipher-suite in 2016 [7]. One of the key benefits of ChaCha20 is its performance especially on resource constrained devices without specific AES instructions. It relays on an IV and a counter, both of which have to be unique to ensure that encryption is not compromised. In our implementation, initialization vector (IV) is hardcoded and tied with the specific image version while the counter, as recommended, always starts from 0. Since we can control the counter, we can also handle one of the main issues, the so-called out-of-order blocks. With block ciphers even if we wanted to decrypt blocks as soon as they are received we would struggle since we have no guarantee of block order while with ChaCha20 we can just provide the correct offset using counter.

To handle encrypted images we also need a way to handle and protect symmetric key stored on the device required for the decryption. To increase the performance we encrypt all application images using only a single symmetric key. Alternatively, it is possible to use Amazon's feature of specifying an update

for group of things to partition devices in groups and use different symmetric keys for each group. In both cases, on each device, this key is encrypted and stored in encrypted form using unique device specific key. We decided to use Physical Unclonable Function (PUF) based on SRAM as a way to derive a device specific key [12]. The main benefit of using a SRAM PUF is avoiding the need of storing generated key both in flash or RAM or using hardcoded key if it is not currently required for decryption of main symmetric key. SRAM PUF usage comes only at cost of reserving a small amount SRAM space (less than 1KB) for calculating deterministic 256 bit device key tied to a specific device, making it feasible even for the resource-constrained devices. SRAM PUFs are based on fact that uninitialized SRAM memory, due to small physical variations during the production process, has random start values. Based on readings of these values in uninitialized state it is possible to uniquely identify a device in question. The variations introduced during the production can not be controlled by the manufacturer, hence making them unclonable.

4 Reference Implementation

In this section we will briefly discuss the STM B-L475E-IOT01A board we used for our reference implementation and implementation specifics related to it.

Selected board is using STM32L475VG MCU with ARM Cortex M4 processor. STM32L475VG provides 128 KB of SRAM (including 32 KB of SRAM with parity checks) and 1MB of flash split in two banks. STM32L4 comes with stage 1 bootloader in ROM system memory programmed by ST during production. This bootloader is mainly tasked with downloading the application image to the internal flash memory through one of the available serial peripherals. The B-L475E-IOT01A, due to it's low hardware resources and popularity of the STM32 MCU family was selected as target platform for our implementation. For our use case, we have implemented stage 2 bootloader implementing required functionality required for the Amazon OTA update process. Our second stage bootloader takes approximately 27KB of RAM. Due to size limits we have split free flash memory into two segments of 464KB, creating two slots from which we can run application images (Figure 2). On each update currently unused segment is overwritten. Old application image is kept until we can verify that it is functioning properly after which, to prevent rollback, we delete former version. For main application image we relied on stock Amazon FreeRTOS MQTT example in which we integrated OTA Agent library. We implemented PAL layer since B-L475E-IOT01A was not officially supported by the Amazon for the OTA updates. During our implementation, one of main hurdles was identifying issue and supporting TLS connection with elliptic curve based certificates. The B-L475E-IOT01A uses Wi-Fi module from Inventek, ISM43362-M3G-L44, to speedup connection process. Unfortunately it currently does not support establishing TLS connection using elliptic curve keys, an issue being investigated by the vendor [3]. As a workaround we stopped offloading TLS to WiFi module and used mbedTLS library. This change introduces slower connection time, as

TLS is now performed on the Cortex M4 processor, as well as increase around 30KB in code size.

For switch to mbedTLS [9], we modified FreeRTOS by deleting project level define `USE_OFFLOAD_SSL`. Also we had to increase available stack and heap memory by modifying `democonfigDEMO_STACKSIZE` and `configTOTAL_HEAP_SIZE` defines in (`aws_demo_config.h` and `FreeRTOSConfig.h`) as well as increasing MQTT timeout by changing `MQTT_TIMEOUT_MS` in `iot_demo_mqtt.c`. The mbedTLS library also supports ChaCha20 stream cipher since version 2.12. ChaCha20 module needs to be enabled in mbedTLS configuration by defining `MBEDTLS_CHACHA20_C`. Compared to default approach, adding image chunk decryption requires only adding symmetric key decryption and modification of PAL function to write new blocks. Code listing of `prvPAL_WriteBlock` function is shown in Listing 1.2. The Average time for decryption and storing 1024 KB block using ChaCha20 on tested board is 28.9 ms while time of storing plaintext block of same size on flash is 23.3 ms. For whole 400KB application image decryption adds only 2.2 seconds of extra processing time, a small increase especially considering low frequency of updates.

```

1 int16_t prvPAL_WriteBlock( OTA_FileContext_t * const C,
2                             uint32_t iOffset,
3                             uint8_t * const pacData,
4                             uint32_t iBlockSize ) {
5     uint8_t output[BLOCK_SIZE];
6     uint32_t counter = floor(iOffset / BLOCK_SIZE) * 16;
7     if (mbedtls_chacha20_crypt(key, nonce, counter,
8                               iBlockSize, pacData, output) == 0 ) {
9         return FLASH_update((uint32_t)((C->pucFile) + iOffset),
10                            (uint64_t *)output, iBlockSize);
11     }
12     return -1;
13 }

```

Listing 1.2. Example of ChaCha20 decryption

For SRAM PUF usage we modified linker script reserving part of the RAM. In this way, we are assured it won't be initialized or overwritten as a consequence enabling us to derive same device key on every request. To handle variations in initialized RAM values we applied fuzzy extractor [15] approach combined with additional data calculated during board enrollment for the error correction.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we have shown the inner working of Amazon OTA update process, explaining OTA Agent library as well as AWS CLI procedure for update creation. Using default implementation as a starting point we presented our approach to harden Amazon OTA update process security. The proposed method adds no new hardware requirements except small increase in required RAM due to allocation of SRAM PUF buffer. Our solution increases both privacy and security

by protecting application image while stored on S3 servers as well as adding new layer of protection during image transfer. Proposed approach could be additionally incremented by storing the encrypted image in flash, performing decryption on each board start-up and running image from SRAM. In both cases, we also require source of trust in form of immutable bootloader which serves as a Root-of-Trust. We have also shown implementation specific challenges and solutions for the B-L475E-IOT01A board.

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7 Appendix A

Fig. 4. Initialization of the OTA Agent library